

THEORY OF TRANSIENT HEAT CONDUCTION IN COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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Summary

A mathematical model is presented to analyze transient heat conduction in composite materials that contain ellipsoidal inclusions in a homogeneous matrix medium. An integro-differential equation for the temperature field in composites is derived using the Green's function for heat conduction. A self-consistent scheme is adopted to derive the effective thermal conductivity and the effective heat capacity. The obtained expression for the effective thermal conductivity is new and shows improvements over previous models.

Introduction

Composite materials have been extensively used in many industries because of their superiority in strength-to-density ratio, stiffness-to-density ratio and corrosion and fatigue resistance. More composite materials are expected to be used in higher temperature environments subjected to a sudden change of temperature in coming years. However, heat conduction in composite materials has not been fully investigated yet except for a simple geometry such as laminated composites (e.g. Refs.(1,2)) or for steady state heat conduction as "byproducts" of the static elastic behavior of composites (e.g. Refs.(3-6)).

In this paper, we address a mathematical model to obtain the effective thermal conductivity and heat capacity of composite materials that contain ellipsoidal inclusions in a homogeneous matrix phase for the time-harmonic temperature change. The heat conduction equation with varying thermal conductivities and heat capacities is converted into an integro-differential equation by introducing the Green's function. An effective medium is sought that exhibits the same overall response as the composite for the same boundary condition. A self-consistent approximation is then adopted to avoid complex statistical operations. The above scheme yields algebraic equations for the effective thermal conductivity and the effective heat capacity. The expression for the effective thermal conductivity is not symmetrical with the matrix thermal conductivity and the inclusion thermal conductivity unlike previous models, thus, reflects the microstructure of the composite more accurately than previous models.

Derivation of Basic Equations

"Composite materials" are defined as those materials whose physical properties are varying with position in a stochastic way. A composite material "a", which consists of n different components, is represented by its characteristic function $\psi_i(\underline{r}, a)$ defined as (Nomura (7))

$$\psi_i(\underline{r}, a) = \begin{matrix} 0 & \text{if } \underline{r} & \text{i-th component} \\ 1 & \text{if } \underline{r} & \text{i-th component} \end{matrix} \quad (1)$$

$i=1, 2, \dots, n$

The ensemble average of a stochastic function $f(\underline{r}, a)$ over the sample space is defined as

$$\langle f(\underline{r}, a) \rangle = \int f(\underline{r}, a) P(da) \quad (2)$$

where $P(da)$ is a probabilistic measure and the integral range is over the entire sample space.

The heat conduction equation for composite materials when the thermal conductivity and the heat capacity are stochastic functions as well as functions of position is expressed as

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} (K_{ij}(\underline{r}, a) \frac{\partial T(\underline{r}, a)}{\partial x_j}) - \rho C \frac{\partial T(\underline{r}, a)}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (3)$$

where $\partial/\partial x_i$ denotes the partial derivative with respect to x_i , $K_{ij}(\underline{r}, a)$ and $(\rho C)(\underline{r}, a)$ are anisotropic thermal conductivity and heat capacity of a particular composite denoted by "a", respectively. The summation convention is used throughout. The thermal conductivity and the heat

capacity can be decomposed into a reference part and a fluctuating part as

$$K_{ij}(\underline{r}, \alpha) = K_{ij}^* + \delta K_{ij}(\underline{r}, \alpha) \quad (4)$$

$$(\rho C)(\underline{r}, \alpha) = (\rho C)^* + \delta(\rho C)(\underline{r}, \alpha) \quad (5)$$

where K_{ij}^* and $(\rho C)^*$ are a constant thermal conductivity and a constant heat capacity of a reference medium which is not specified yet and $\delta K_{ij}(\underline{r}, \alpha)$ and $\delta(\rho C)(\underline{r}, \alpha)$ are fluctuating quantities from those of the reference medium. Substitution of Eqs.(4) and (5) into Eq.(3) yields

$$K_{ij}^* \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial x_i \partial x_j} - (\rho C)^* \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = - \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \left(\delta K_{ij} \frac{\partial T}{\partial x_j} \right) + \delta(\rho C) \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} \quad (6)$$

We seek a time-harmonic solution to Eq.(6). By setting

$$T(\underline{r}, t, \alpha) = T(\underline{r}, \alpha) \exp(-i\omega t) \quad (7)$$

where ω is angular frequency, Eq.(6) becomes

$$\begin{aligned} K_{ij}^* \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial x_i \partial x_j} + i\omega(\rho C)^* T \\ = - \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \left(\delta K_{ij} \frac{\partial T}{\partial x_j} \right) - \delta(\rho C) i\omega T \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

Eq.(8) can be solved formally by regarding the right hand side of (8) as an imaginary heat source as

$$\begin{aligned} T(\underline{r}, \alpha) = \Gamma^A(\underline{r}) + \int \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i'} \left(\delta K_{ij}(\underline{r}', \alpha) \frac{\partial T(\underline{r}', \alpha)}{\partial x_j'} \right) g(\underline{r} - \underline{r}') d\underline{r}' \\ + \int \delta(\rho C)(\underline{r}', \alpha) i\omega T(\underline{r}', \alpha) g(\underline{r} - \underline{r}') \delta \underline{r}' \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

where $\Gamma^A(\underline{r})$ is a temperature field for the homogeneous medium with K_{ij}^* and $(\rho C)^*$. The integral range in Eq.(9) is over the whole material points. In Eq.(9), $g(\underline{r} - \underline{r}')$ is the time-reduced Green's function for heat conduction defined as

$$K_{ij}^* \frac{\partial^2 g(\underline{r} - \underline{r}')}{\partial x_i \partial x_j} + i\omega(\rho C)^* g(\underline{r} - \underline{r}') = -\delta(\underline{r} - \underline{r}') \quad (10)$$

where $\delta(\underline{r})$ is the Dirac delta function. Eq.(9) can be rearranged using

integration by parts to

$$T(\underline{r}, \alpha) = T^A(\underline{r}) + \int \delta K_{ij}(\underline{r}, \alpha) \frac{\partial T(\underline{r}', \alpha)}{\partial x_j'} \frac{\partial g(\underline{r} - \underline{r}')}{\partial x_i'} d\underline{r}' + \int i\omega \delta(\rho C)(\underline{r}', \alpha) T(\underline{r}', \alpha) g(\underline{r} - \underline{r}') d\underline{r}' \quad (11)$$

Note that Eq.(11) is formal because it contains $T(\underline{r}, \alpha)$ in both sides.

Self-Consistent Approximation

When the composite has N kinds of inclusions embedded in a homogeneous matrix phase, it is convenient to rewrite $\delta K_{ij}(\underline{r}, \alpha)$ and $\delta(\rho C)(\underline{r}, \alpha)$ as

$$\delta K_{ij}(\underline{r}, \alpha) = (K_{ij}^m - K_{ij}^*) + \sum_{n=1}^N (K_{ij}^n - K_{ij}^m) \gamma_n(\underline{r}, \alpha) \quad (12)$$

$$\delta(\rho C)(\underline{r}, \alpha) = ((\rho C)^m - (\rho C)^*) + \sum_{n=1}^N ((\rho C)^n - (\rho C)^m) \gamma_n(\underline{r}, \alpha) \quad (13)$$

where the quantities with the superscript "m" denote those associated with the matrix phase, K_{ij}^n and $(\rho C)^n$ are the thermal conductivity and the heat capacity of the n -th kind inclusion and $\gamma_n(\underline{r}, \alpha)$ is the characteristic function of the n -th kind inclusion phase defined in Eq.(1). By taking the ensemble average of Eq.(11) with the substitution of Eqs.(12) and (13), we have

$$\begin{aligned} \langle T(\underline{r}, \alpha) \rangle &= T^A(\underline{r}) + i\omega ((\rho C)^m - (\rho C)^*) \int g(\underline{r} - \underline{r}') \langle T(\underline{r}', \alpha) \rangle d\underline{r}' \\ &+ i\omega \sum_{n=1}^N ((\rho C)^n - (\rho C)^m) \int g(\underline{r} - \underline{r}') \langle \gamma_n(\underline{r}', \alpha) T(\underline{r}', \alpha) \rangle d\underline{r}' \\ &+ (K_{ij}^m - K_{ij}^*) \int \frac{\partial g(\underline{r} - \underline{r}')}{\partial x_i'} \left\langle \frac{\partial T(\underline{r}', \alpha)}{\partial x_j} \right\rangle d\underline{r}' \\ &+ \sum_{n=1}^N (K_{ij}^n - K_{ij}^m) \int \frac{\partial g(\underline{r} - \underline{r}')}{\partial x_i'} \langle \gamma_n(\underline{r}', \alpha) \frac{\partial T(\underline{r}', \alpha)}{\partial x_j} \rangle d\underline{r}' \quad (14) \end{aligned}$$

So far K_{ij}^* and $(\rho C)^*$ were not specified yet. We now adopt the self-consistent scheme that K_{ij}^* and $(\rho C)^*$ are chosen in such a way that the ensemble average of $T(\underline{r}, \alpha)$ is equal to $T^A(\underline{r})$. For such a situation, the "effective" thermal conductivity K_{ij}^* and the "effective" heat capacity $(\rho C)^*$ are defined as the properties of the "equivalent" homogeneous medium that produces the same ensemble averaged temperature as the composite as

$$\langle T(\underline{r}, a) \rangle = T^A(\underline{r}) \quad (15)$$

We further adopt the following replacement of each quantity in Eq.(14) as

$$\langle \mathcal{V}_n(\underline{r}, a) T(\underline{r}, a) \rangle = V_n T^A \quad (16)$$

$$\langle \partial T(\underline{r}, a) / \partial x_j \rangle = \partial T^A / \partial x_j \quad (17)$$

$$\langle \mathcal{V}_n(\underline{r}, a) \partial T(\underline{r}, a) / \partial x_i \rangle = V_n A_{ij}^{(n)}(\underline{r}) \partial T^A / \partial x_j \quad (18)$$

where V_n is the volume fraction of the n -th kind inclusion, $A_{ij}^{(n)}$ is a proportionality factor of the temperature inside the n -th kind inclusion when a single inclusion is placed in a homogeneous medium with the temperature gradient $\partial T^A / \partial x_j$ applied at remote distances as a boundary condition. In Eqs.(16)-(18), we adopted 1) the integral over the sample space is exchangeable with differentiation on the position, 2) the ergodic assumption that the ensemble average can be replaced by the spatial average. Eqs.(16)-(18) imply that the temperature field inside each inclusion is approximated by the boundary temperature T^A while the temperature gradient field inside each inclusion is approximated by the temperature gradient field when a single inclusion is placed in a homogeneous medium. This approximation is called quasi-static approximation in solid mechanics (Berryman (8)) which is correct to $\mathcal{O}(\omega^4)$ and exact as $\omega \rightarrow 0$ (Gubernatis et al. (9)). Therefore, by combining Eqs.(14)-(18), we obtain the following equations for K_{ij}^* and $(\rho C)^*$ as

$$(\rho C)^m - (\rho C)^* + \sum_{n=1}^N V_n ((\rho C)^n - (\rho C)^m) = 0 \quad (19)$$

$$K_{ij}^m - K_{ij}^* + \sum_{n=1}^N V_n A_{ik}^{(n)} (K_{kj}^n - K_{kj}^m) = 0 \quad (20)$$

If each inclusion is of ellipsoidal shape and aligned unidirectionally along the x_3 -axis, it can be shown that

$$A_{11} = A_{21} = \frac{1}{1 + (K^n - K^m) G_{11}} \quad (21)$$

$$A_{33} = \frac{1}{1 + (K^n - K^m) G_{33}} \quad (22)$$

where

$$G_{11} = \frac{1}{K_{11}^m} \int_0^1 \frac{(1-x^2)}{1 - (1 - \frac{K_{33}^m}{\rho^2 K_{11}^m}) x^2} dx \quad (23)$$

$$G_{33} = \frac{1}{\rho^2 K_{11}^m} \int_0^1 \frac{x^2}{K_{33}^m - \frac{x^2}{1 - (1 - \frac{x^2}{\rho^2 K_{11}^m})^2}} dx \quad (24)$$

In Eqs.(23) and (24), ρ is the aspect ratio of the inclusion (ratio of major axis/minor axis).

Eq.(20) can be solved for $(\rho C)^*$ as

$$(\rho C)^* = V_m (\rho C)^m + V_i (\rho C)^i \quad (25)$$

Eq.(25) shows that the effective heat capacity follows the rule of mixtures, which can be also derived by considering the balance of mass.

Discussions

Eq.(21) can be applied to several types of composites. For example, if the composite contains spherical shaped (particulate) inclusions ($\rho=1$), we find

$$K^* = K^m + \frac{V_i (K^i - K^m)}{1 + \frac{K^i - K^m}{3 K^*}} \quad (26)$$

Eq.(26) can be easily solved as

$$K^* = \{ (9(K^m)^2 V_i^2 - 24(K^m)^2 V_i + 4(K^m)^2 - 18K^m V_i^2 K^i + 30K^m V_i K^i + 4K^m K^i + 9V_i^2 (K^i)^2 - 6V_i (K^i)^2 + (K^i)^2)^{1/2} - 3K^m V_i + 4K^m + 3V_i K^i - K^i \} / 6 \quad (27)$$

It should be noted that Eq.(27) is not symmetrical with the interchange of the matrix phase and the inclusion phase keeping the same volume fraction each other. This comes from the decomposition of Eqs.(12) and (13).

Figure 1 shows the comparison of Eq.(27) with the conventional self-consistent model (Hashin (3)) and upper and lower bounds derived by Hashin and Shtrikman (10) for the composite that contains spherical inclusions. It is seen that our result lies within the upper and lower bounds of Hashin and Shtrikman and slightly below the conventional self-consistent method. The conventional self-consistent method has been criticized for overestimating the effective quantity. Our result shows the improvement in this respect.

Figure 2 shows the variation of the effective axial thermal conductivities K_{11}^* with the inclusion aspect ratios. As seen from Figure 2, the effective axial thermal conductivity exhibits the "rule of mixtures" for the inclusion aspect ratio over 50 which agrees with

Figure 1 - The effective thermal conductivity for spherical inclusion composites. $K^i/K^m=20$.

Figure 2 - Variations of the axial effective thermal conductivity with the inclusion aspect ratios. $K^i/K^m=20$, $V_i=0.3$.

the result by Nomura and Chou (11).

It is expected that at high frequency regions both the effective thermal conductivity and the effective heat capacity depend on the frequency. Further analysis will be reported in the near future.

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